

in nonaqueous solvents. As a result of porosity these resins may be used for the exchange of big ions of the type $(NR_4)^{4+}$ and hence, in pharmaceutical industry.

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Synthesis of Aryl Thioureas and Related Compounds as Potential Fungicides

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THE pesticidal activity of substituted thioureas is due to the presence of N—C=S group. Various 4-thiazolidones are shown to possess pesticidal¹, miticidal², antimicrobial^{3,4}, antibacterial⁵, antitubercular⁶, amaebicidal⁷, and fungicidal⁸⁻¹⁰ activities. 3-Aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones have also been reported for their fungicidal activity¹¹. Keeping this in view some aryl thioureas, 4-thiazolidones and related compounds were prepared.

Methylantranilate was condensed with aryl isothiocyanate to yield *N*-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-*N'*-aryl thioureas (I). I on heating with chloroacetic acid and fused sodium acetate gave the corresponding 3-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones (II), which with anhydrous sodium acetate and an aldehyde produced 5-arylideno-3-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones (III). III on bromination yielded the corresponding dibromides (IV).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected and purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Structure

assigned to II was confirmed by hydrolysis. The structure of the compounds was confirmed by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectra. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 190 spectrophotometer and nmr on Varian EM 360 spectrophotometer at 60 MHz.

***N*-*o*-Carbomethoxyphenyl-*N'*-arylthioureas (I):** A methanolic solution of methyl anthranilate (0.01 *M*) and arylisothiocyanate (0.01 *M*) was refluxed for 3 h and cooled. The product separating out was filtered, washed and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 1.

3-*o*-Carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones (II): A methanolic solution of thiourea (I) (0.01 *M*), chloroacetic acid (0.01 *M*) and fused sodium acetate (2.0 g) was refluxed for 5 h, cooled and poured into water. The solid separating out was filtered, washed with water and crystallised with aqueous ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are given in Table 2.

Structural confirmation of II: A methanolic solution (10 ml) of the above 4-thiazolidone (1.0 g) and conc. HCl (2 ml) was refluxed for 3 to 4 h. Methanol was distilled off and the residue poured into water. The precipitate obtained was washed with water and crystallised. Each one of the compounds (II) was hydrolysed and the resulting compound 3-(*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl)thiazolidine-2,4-dione, had the same m.p. 240°. M.m.p. remained the same. It could not, however, be synthesised.

5-Arylideno-3-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones (III): A mixture of 3-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-one (0.01 *M*),

TABLE 1—*N*-*o*-CARBOMETHOXYPHENYL-*N'*-ARYLTHIOUREAS (I)*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Fungicidal activity, Conc. 10 ppm		
					<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
1.	H**	285	95.6	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	30.2	30.0	33.2
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	245	94.7	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	31.3	31.4	35.3
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	286	96.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	32.8	31.8	35.0

* Elemental analyses in good agreement with the calculated ones.

** ν_{max} 3200 (N—H stretch), 1730 (C=O aryl ester), 1080 cm⁻¹ (C—S) and 760 (*ortho*-substituted benzene); δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.6 (s, 2H, NH), 4.1 (s, 3H, COOCH₃) and 7.4-8.0 (m, 9H, Ar).

TABLE 2—3-*o*-CARBOMETHOXYPHENYL-2-ARYLIMINOTHIAZOLID-4-ONES (II)*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Fungicidal activity, Conc. 10 ppm		
					<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
4.	H**	200	82.7	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S	32.5	32.0	35.5
5.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	225	85.5	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S	33.0	32.4	36.5
6.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	246	90.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S	33.2	32.2	38.7

* Explanation as in Table 1.

** ν_{max} 1700 (C=O aryl ester), 1630 (CO—N tert-amine), 1600 (C=N) and 760 cm⁻¹ (*ortho*-substituted benzene); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.5 (s, 2H, CH₂), 3.32 (s, 3H, COOCH₃) and 7.3-8.0 (m, 9H, Ar).

TABLE 3—ARYLIDENO-3-*o*-CARBOMETHOXYPHENYL-2-ARYLIMINOTHIAZOLID-4-ONES (III)*

Sl. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Fungicidal activity Conc. 10 ppm		
						<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
7.	-H	-H**	291	75.4	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—
8.	-H	-OH	295	77.6	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄ S	40.6	40.3	42.5
9.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	-H	271	79.5	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ S	43.7	43.5	47.8
10.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	-OH	265	75.6	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—
11.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	-H	276	80.2	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—
12.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	-OH	220	82.3	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ S	44.6	44.7	48.3

* Explanation as in Table 1.

** ν_{max} 720 (C=O aryl ester), 1660 (CO—N tert-amide), 1620 (C=N), 760 (*ortho*-, *mono*-substituted benzene) and 690 cm⁻¹ (S-).

TABLE 4—5-ARYLIDENO-3-*o*-CARBOMETHOXYPHENYL-2-ARYLIMINOTHIAZOLID-4-ONE DIBROMIDES (IV)

Sl. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Fungicidal activity, Conc. 10 ppm		
						<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
13.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	OH	240	69.5	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—
14.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H**	210	72.3	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	47.5	47.0	50.3
15.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	OH	193	70.6	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	48.7	49.0	52.5
						75.4	78.2	72.8
						73.5	79.5	78.3

Memcge
Blitox 50 WP

* Explanation as in Table 1.

** ν_{max} 1730 (C=O aryl ester), 1650 (CO—N tert-amide), 1620 (C=N), 800 (*para*-substituted benzene), 760 (*ortho*-, *mono*-substituted benzene), 710 (—S—) and 680 cm⁻¹ (C—Br).

arylaldehyde (0.01 *M*) and anhydrous sodium acetate (2.0 g) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) for 6 h and cooled. The resulting solution was poured into water and the solid separating was filtered, washed and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are given in Table 3.

5-Arylideno-3-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazol-4-one dibromides (IV): 5-Arylideno-3-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-one (0.005 *M*) was dissolved in minimum amount of chloroform. To this, Br₂ (0.005 *M*) in chloroform was added dropwise with swirling. The solution was kept in an ice-bath for 4 h and shaken intermittently. On evaporation a solid residue was obtained which was washed with water and crystallised from

aqueous ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are given in Table 4.

Fungicidal screening: The compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *A. flavus*, *H. oryzae* and *C. sacchari* by agar-plate technique¹⁸ at three different concentration, viz. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. Two commercial fungicides Memcge and Blitox 50 WP have also been tested under similar conditions to compare the result. The number of replications in each case was three. The percentage inhibition of growth of fungus colony is given by the following expression.

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = \frac{C-T}{C} \times 100$$

where C = diameter of fungus colony (mm) in control after 96 h,

T = diameter of fungus colony (mm) in presence of test chemical after 96 h.

Results and Discussion

Most of the compounds reported herein have been screened for their antifungal activity against *A. flavus*, *H. oryzae* and *C. sacchari* and found to possess moderate to fairly good level of fungicidal activity. However, they are slightly more toxic against *C. sacchari* than *A. flavus* and *M. oryzae*. In general, introduction of different groups and their position did not affect the toxicity to any marked degree. However, introduction of methyl group resulted in an increase of fungicidal activity. A comparison of compounds of Tables 1-4 shows that the dibromides (VI) are little more active than compounds III which in turn show slightly better activity than compounds II. The least active are the compounds I (Table 1). Compounds 14 and 15 are more active due to the presence of bromine.

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Synthesis of Thiazolyl Compounds as Potential Fungicides

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THIAZOLES have been reported as insecticidal¹, antibacterial², antitubercular³, antifungal⁴, herbicidal⁵, pesticidal⁶ and local anaesthetic⁷ agents. Acridines have been reported as insecticides⁸ and fungicides⁹, and compounds containing triazole ring have shown fungicidal¹⁰, bactericidal¹¹ and pesticidal¹² activity. In view of these facts it was worth investigating the compounds having both the moieties.

2-Amino-4-phenylthiazole was condensed with 5-chloroacridine to yield 4-phenyl-2-(acridin-5-yl)aminothiazole (I). 4-Phenyl-(thiazol-2-yl)-aminoacetylhydrazine (VI) was reacted with 5-chloroacridine to yield *N*-(acridin-5-yl)-*N*'-(4''-phenylthiazole-2''-yl)-aminoacetylhydrazine (III). I on treatment with arylisothiocyanate yielded *N*-aryl-*N*'-(4''-phenylthiazol-2''-yl)aminoacetylthiosemicarbazide (IV) which on alkaline cyclisation yielded the corresponding triazole (V).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected and purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Structure of